

IMPORTANCE OF ROSEMARY PLANT

Rahmonov Rajabali Bozor o`g`li

Tashkent State Agrarian University

Sultanova Gulbakhor Abdijalolovna

Tashkent State Agrarian University

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Abstract: Rosemary officinalis or common rosemary Rosmarinus officinalis is a species of semi-shrub and shrubby forms of evergreen plants of the genus Rosemary of the Lamiaceae family. The plant is strongly branched, pleasantly smelling, evergreen and thermophilic. It sometimes reaches a height of two meters, in one place it can grow up to 10 years. The root system is well developed, penetrates to a depth of 4 meters. Old branches are lignified, covered with gray-brown bark, young branches are green, tetrahedral.

Key words: Rosemary plant, importance, medicinal properties, Chemical composition.

Rosemary leaves are linear, reminiscent of needles, leathery and glossy on top, barely curled around the edge and felt-pubescent below. In May, the flowering of the plant begins: light blue fragrant flowers appear in the upper part of the shoots, collected in false whorls. Rosemary is an excellent honey plant, pollinated by insects. Rosemary seeds are small, brownish. The plant is unpretentious to soils, does not like highly moistened places, does not tolerate frosts of more than 10 degrees.

Chemical composition

Rosemary essential oil contains cineol, camphor, limonene, borneol, pinene, tannins, resins, bitterness. Iron, phosphorus, magnesium, sodium, potassium and zinc, which are part of the plant, have a beneficial effect on the immune system of the human body.

Pharmacological properties

Rosemary is an excellent immune booster. The plant is used for hypotension, general exhaustion, sexual weakness. The following medicinal properties of rosemary are known: anti-inflammatory, diuretic, tonic, wound healing, choleric, antidepressant, antioxidant. It also has a softening and antitussive effect in case of colds.

Rosemary oil is an excellent antiseptic. It is used to treat skin diseases (acne, furunculosis, eczema), healing of infected wounds. The active components of the essential oil improve local blood circulation, have a disinfectant and tonic effect on the skin. Rosemary contains several types of antioxidants, of which rosmarinic acid has the greatest anti-aging effect. Therefore, cosmetic products for face and body skin care with plant extract have a beneficial effect on dry, problematic and aging skin.

The properties of rosemary are unique, since the plant's phytoncides are able to neutralize up to 80% of indoor microbes, including staphylococci, streptococci, E. coli and yeast fungi.

Application

Rosemary oil is used in dermatology for the treatment of acne, eczema, infected purulent wounds, furunculosis. It has antiseptic, antioxidant properties.

Due to the unique anti-inflammatory activity of rosemary, in particular rosmarinic acid, which is part of it, the leaves of the plant are used in the treatment of certain ailments of the urinary system: glomerulonephritis, pyelonephritis, cystitis. Rosemary extract as part of the German

combined preparation Kanefron N in combination with centaury and lovage extracts has an antispasmodic, diuretic and antimicrobial effect.

Rosemary is an excellent stimulant of the body's immune system, renewing strength after debilitating infectious diseases.

Decoctions, infusions of rosemary leaves, baths using the essential oil of the plant are used in folk medicine for the treatment of respiratory diseases, diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, diseases of the cardiovascular system, anemia, hypotension, sciatica, convulsions and nervous disorders.

Rosemary-based products (decoctions and alcoholic infusions, essential oil) are successfully used in folk medicine in the treatment of anemia, stomatitis and gingivitis, pharyngitis, ulcers that are difficult to heal, impotence, sciatica and rheumatism (in the form of therapeutic baths), menopause and leucorrhoea (by douching). For therapeutic purposes, use infusions, decoctions, essential oil of the plant.

Rosemary has been known for its medicinal properties since ancient times. Following the endorsement of the plant and its healing power by the American scientist Sebastian Kneipp, rosemary has been widely recognized in folk medicine. Annual shoots and leaves of the Mediterranean plant are used internally as a tonic and astringent, sedative (for nervous disorders during menopause), analgesic (for stomach cramps, pain in the heart).

It is taken externally in the form of decoctions or alcoholic tinctures for parotitis, thrombophlebitis, for wound healing. Rosemary is effective for stomach cramps, colic in the upper abdomen, rheumatism, gout, low blood pressure. It helps to strengthen the immune system, restores the body's strength after prolonged use of antibiotics and general weakness. The use of rosemary spice in food increases the secretion of gastric juice, improves digestion. In the form of wine, rosemary is a means to increase potency.

Rosemary essential oil treats bronchitis and tracheitis, baths with the addition of a few drops of this healing drug relieve nervous tension, improve mood, give the body strength and vigor. Baths are not recommended to be taken immediately before bedtime.

Healing remedies based on rosemary are effective for intestinal dysfunction, diseases of the abdominal organs, liver and gallbladder, dropsy, vascular and heart diseases, paralysis and convulsions. Regular use of seasoning helps to strengthen the body after prolonged illnesses.

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